

Figure 4B: Induction of ethylene biosynthesis in tomato leaves.

Non-shared letters indicate groups with statistically significant differences; 2-way ANOVA on aligned rank-transformed data, performed separately for mock vs. antiSYS and mock vs. SYS5 pre-treatment:

- for pre-treatment with mock vs. **antiSYS**: global $F_{11,36} = 15.9$, $P = 1.1 \times 10^{-10}$, $R^2_{Efron} = 0.97$;
post-hoc: ART-C contrast test with P -value adjustment acc. to Tukey and $P_{adj.} < 0.05$.
- for pre-treatment with mock vs. **SYS5**: global $F_{3,12} = 2.3$, $P = 0.13$, $R^2_{Efron} = 0.97$
(i.e. no significant difference between group combinations, as pre-treatment with SYS5 peptide has no effect no ethylene response).

